

Title	D3.2 Reusable methodology and template for national EOSC-aligned PID Strategies
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Executive Summary

This document provides a clear and practical method to help countries update their national Persistent Identifier (PID) strategies so they align with the expectations of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The goal is to make sure that national plans for using and managing PIDs are compatible with European standards, easy to implement and responsive to the needs of local research communities.

The methodology is based on evidence gathered during a project funded in May 2025 under the RDA TIGER Cascade Grant Scheme designed to support an EOSC-aligned national PID recommendation for Ireland. It uses a simple, structured approach to compare an existing national PID strategy with the EOSC PID Policy. This comparison highlights what is already aligned, what is partly aligned, and what may need improvement. These insights then form the basis for practical recommendations for strengthening national PID systems.

To support this process, the document includes a reusable checklist that countries can use to assess their strategies. The checklist is designed to be high-level and easy to follow, enabling countries to quickly identify gaps and plan updates.

Finally, the report points readers to a set of useful European and international resources—such as tools, templates, and guidance from EOSC projects—that can be adapted rather than reinvented. This supports consistency across Europe while reducing the workload for national teams.

Overall, this document aims to make the process of aligning national PID strategies with EOSC guidance straightforward, transparent and achievable for countries at different stages of PID adoption.

Contents

Executive Summary.....	1
1. Introduction	2
2. Reusable Methodology for Aligning an Existing National PID Strategy with the EOSC PID Policy	2
2.1 Evidence-Based and Practical Approach.....	3
2.2 Use of a Structured Analytical Framework.....	3
2.3 Gap Analysis as the Foundation for Recommendations	3
2.4 Development of Recommendations	3
2.5 Guiding Principles.....	4
3. EOSC PID Policy Alignment Checklist.....	5
3.1 Principles	5
3.2 Generic PID Definitions	5
3.3 Roles and Responsibilities	5
3.4 PID Applications	6
3.5 PID Types.....	6
3.6 PID Services and Service Providers	6
3.7 Governance and Sustainability	7
3.8 Legal and Ethical Considerations (GDPR).....	7
4. Resources to Support Your Update.....	8

1. Introduction

This document provides a reusable, straightforward method to assess an existing national PID strategy against the EOSC PID Policy. Using a clear analytical framework and an easy-to-follow checklist, it helps countries identify strengths, gaps and areas for improvement. It also points to European tools and guidance that can be adapted locally, reducing duplication and supporting consistent, sustainable PID practices across Europe.

This deliverable was funded in May 2025 under the RDA TIGER Cascade Grant Scheme, awarded jointly to Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) and HEAnet, Ireland's National Research and Education Network and EOSC Mandated Organisation.

2. Reusable Methodology for Aligning an Existing National PID Strategy with the EOSC PID Policy

This methodology provides a practical, evidence-based process that countries can use to update or refine their existing national PID strategies to ensure alignment with the EOSC PID Policy. It is

designed to support realistic, locally implementable recommendations while maintaining coherence with European expectations for interoperability, FAIRness and sustainability.

2.1 Evidence-Based and Practical Approach

The methodology is grounded in a structured review of national PID practices, relevant European guidance, and the experience of stakeholders involved in PID implementation. Its aim is to ensure that recommendations are both aligned with EOSC requirements and feasible within national contexts.

2.2 Use of a Structured Analytical Framework

The alignment process is based on a systematic comparison between the existing national PID strategy and the EOSC PID Policy. A structured analytical framework is applied using core elements of the EOSC PID Policy as the organising headings. These include:

- Principles
- Generic PID Definitions
- Roles and Responsibilities
- PID applications
- PID Types
- Governance and Sustainability
- Legal and Ethical Considerations (GDPR)

Although not a standalone section in the EOSC PID Policy, legal and ethical considerations often arise across multiple policy areas. For this reason, they are included as an additional category in the analysis framework.

Each component of the national PID strategy is reviewed against these criteria to determine:

- the level of alignment
- gaps or inconsistencies
- areas requiring further development to support EOSC interoperability

The analysis framework may evolve throughout the process in response to stakeholder feedback or emerging policy requirements.

2.3 Gap Analysis as the Foundation for Recommendations

The structured comparison highlights areas where improvements or updates are needed. These identified gaps form the basis for all recommendations.

For each gap, the methodology recommends reviewing outputs from relevant European initiatives — such as FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT and other EOSC implementation projects — to identify tools, templates, guidance and services that can be adapted nationally. This avoids duplication of work and ensures consistency with wider European developments.

2.4 Development of Recommendations

Recommendations should be organised in line with the governance and operational structure of the national PID ecosystem. In most countries, two levels are relevant:

1. **Strategic governance bodies** – responsible for national coordination, policy alignment and oversight.

2. **Operational or support services** – responsible for technical guidance, community support, training and implementation.

Draft recommendations should be refined through internal review, consultation with national communities and stakeholders, and alignment with parallel open science or research infrastructure planning activities.

2.5 Guiding Principles

The following principles should guide the analysis and the development of recommendations:

- **Clarity and practicality** – recommendations must be easy to understand and implement.
- **Alignment with European expectations** – ensuring national PID practices support full participation in EOSC.
- **Reuse before creating new materials** – favouring adaptation of existing European tools and guidance.
- **Community relevance** – ensuring recommendations reflect the needs and capacities of national institutions.
- **Ability to evolve** – supporting regular updates as EOSC standards and national requirements change.

3. EOSC PID Policy Alignment Checklist

A reusable, high-level “yes/no/partial” checklist to assess a country’s existing National PID Strategy against the EOSC PID Policy

3.1 Principles

EOSC PID Policy Section 2 sets out ten principles for viable, trusted long-term PID infrastructure.

Assessment Question	Yes	Mostly	No/Unclear
Does your strategy explicitly commit to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?			
Does your strategy emphasise interoperability between PID systems?			
Does your strategy accommodate both human and machine interoperability?			
Does your governance structure include representation from your national EOSC node or EOSC Mandated Organisation?			
Are your strategy review cycles aligned with EOSC timelines (minimum 3-year review)?			

3.2 Generic PID Definitions

EOSC PID Policy Section 3 defines requirements for global uniqueness, persistence, and resolvability.

Assessment Question	Yes	Mostly	No/Unclear
Does your strategy address how PIDs expose machine-actionable metadata through APIs?			
Does your strategy reference Kernel Information Profiles (KIPs) or minimal metadata standards?			
Does your strategy provide guidance on metadata structures that make PIDs actionable by machines?			
Does your strategy address how PID metadata should be registered in open registries?			
Does your strategy require PIDs to remain resolvable even when the referenced object is deleted (tombstones)?			

3.3 Roles and Responsibilities

EOSC PID Policy Section 4 defines six key roles in PID infrastructure.

Assessment Question	Yes	Mostly	No/Unclear
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Does your strategy adopt the EOSC-defined roles: PID Authority, PID Service Provider, PID Manager, PID Owner, PID User?			
Have you mapped national stakeholders to these specific EOSC roles?			

3.4 PID Applications

EOSC PID Policy Section 5 sets expectations for PID use across research lifecycle.

Assessment Question	Yes	Mostly	No/Unclear
Does your strategy provide guidance on when to issue new PIDs vs. new versions?			
Does your strategy address appropriate granularity levels for different entity types?			
Does your strategy provide procedures for handling deleted items (tombstoning)?			
Does your strategy address versioning policies and best practices?			
Does your strategy specify that PIDs should not be reassigned?			
Does your strategy address secure mechanisms for PIDs referencing confidential data?			

3.5 PID Types

EOSC PID Policy Section 6 addresses PIDs for digital, physical, and conceptual entities.

Assessment Question	Yes	Mostly	No/Unclear
Does your strategy cover PIDs beyond the priority four (DOI, ORCID, ROR, RAiD)?			
Does your strategy address PIDs for physical samples and instruments?			
Does your strategy address PIDs for conceptual entities (vocabularies, workflows)?			
Do you have a mechanism to assess and integrate new/emerging PID types?			
Does your strategy include a process for monitoring international PID developments?			

3.6 PID Services and Service Providers

EOSC PID Policy Section 7 specifies expectations for PID Service Providers

Assessment Question	Yes	Mostly	No/Unclear

Does your strategy specify that basic PID services should be free at point of use?			
Does your strategy reference Technology Readiness Levels (TRL 8/9) for PID services?			
Does your strategy require PID Service Providers to have sustainability plans?			
Does your strategy require open APIs for PID services?			
Do you have criteria to help institutions evaluate PID Service Providers?			
Does your strategy reference EOSC certification processes for PID Service Providers?			

3.7 Governance and Sustainability

EOSC PID Policy Section 8 establishes principles for community governance

Assessment Question	Yes	Mostly	No/Unclear
Does your governance structure operate with stakeholder input (advisory boards)?			
Do you have mechanisms to gather feedback and adapt services?			
Do you have performance monitoring and regular reporting to stakeholders?			
Is your budgeting transparent and cost-effectiveness demonstrated?			
Do PID Service Providers have documented exit plans?			
Does your governance explicitly link to EOSC governance structures?			

3.8 Legal and Ethical Considerations (GDPR)

EOSC PID Policy addresses GDPR compliance for PIDs

Assessment Question	Yes	Mostly	No/Unclear
Does your strategy address GDPR implications of PIDs containing personal data?			
Does your strategy provide guidance on lawful bases for processing PID-related personal data?			
Does your strategy address how to handle erasure requests while maintaining PID resolvability?			
Does your strategy include guidance on metadata minimisation for PIDs?			
Do you have guidance for institutions to handle GDPR requests related to PIDs?			

4. Resources to Support Your Update

EOSC PID Policy: European Commission. (2020). A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

Ireland's National PID Strategy and Roadmap: Brown, J et al. (2024) Interoperability, openness, and impact: Recommendations and roadmap for an Irish PID Strategy. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.sn00qt29n>

Ireland's Gap Analysis: Doran, M., & O'Neill, J. (2025). D2.1 Gap Analysis Between Ireland's PID Strategy and the EOSC PID Policy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17700383>

Ireland's Recommendations: Doran, M., & O'Neill, J. (2025). D4.2 EOSC Compatible National PID Recommendation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17721148>

FAIRCORE4EOSC: <https://faircore4eosc.eu/> (tools: PID Graph, DTR, MSCR, CAT)

FAIR-IMPACT: <https://fair-impact.eu/> (guidance: PID implementation, versioning, legal interoperability).

EOSC Association: Contact your national [EOSC Association mandated organisation](#).

Research Data Alliance (RDA): National Persistent Identifier Strategies IG and PID-related working groups.